

REMOTE VS. OFFICE WORKERS AND GREEN ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR: EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF WORK SETTING ON PRO-ENVIRONMENTAL ACTIONS

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine whether office workers and remote workers differ in their overall levels of Green Organization Citizenship Behavior. Green OCB comprises 3 dimensions: eco-initiatives, eco-civic engagement and eco-helping. The individuals aged 22 to 35 working in IT sector were chosen as the sample of this study. The data was collected through google forms using Green Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (GOCB / OCBE) scale developed by Paillé et al. (2012). The inferential statistics of independent samples t- test was used to compare the means of the two groups across three dimensions. The finding indicated that there are no statistical differences between the two groups, suggesting workplace location does not meaningfully influence employee's voluntary environmental behaviour. These findings will help organization design Green HRM and sustainable strategies suited across diverse work modes.

Keywords: *Green OCB, Remote work, Office work, IT sector, Green HRM*

Introduction

Organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) is an “individual behaviour that is discretionary, not explicitly recognized by the formal reward system, and that in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organization” (Organ, 1988). OCB has been categorized into two dimensions; OCBI (individual oriented) and OCBO (organization oriented) (Fan Q, 2023). Based on this, the concept of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour for the Environment (OCBE) or Green Organizational Citizenship Behaviour have been

developed. OCBE focuses on employees' voluntary, unrewarded employee behaviours that contribute to environmental improvement. Eco-initiatives refer to voluntary and proactive actions taken by employees to improve environmental performance, even when not formally required. Eco-civic engagement involve participation in organizational or community environmental programs and awareness activities. Eco helping refer to voluntary efforts to assist and encourage coworkers in adopting eco-friendly practices. Together these three are the key dimensions of OCBE ((Paille, 2012)). These behaviours capture the important behaviour linkage between HRM practices and sustainability outcomes and these behaviours can vary across different work arrangements. With the rise of remote and hybrid work, especially in the IT sector, the workplace context may influence how employees demonstrate environmental citizenship. The office workers are more likely exposed to visible organizational initiatives to improve internal physical environment conditions, whereas the remote workers express eco-friendly behaviours more in a self-initiated way. However, few have directly compared how these two groups differ in the three dimensions of OCBE and thus this study looks to compare remote and office-based employees in their engagement in OCBE.

Literature review

Organizational Citizenship Behaviour refers to extra role behaviours that help organization function effectively. The seven major categories identified by (Philip M. Podsakoff, 2000) are helping, sportsmanship, organizational loyalty, compliance, individual initiative, civic virtue, and self-development, these highlight the wide behavioural range of OCB. According to (Jeffrey A. LePine, 2002), the five dimensions of OCB are job satisfaction, organizational commitment, fairness, leader support, and conscientiousness. These are interrelated and suggest that OCB is a general unified predisposition of pro-social behaviour.

The most significant antecedents of Green HRM are ethical and transformational leadership, CSR orientation, and green intellectual capital. These nurture the moral norms of employees and the pro-environmental attitude and enhances in-role green behaviour and voluntary OCBE (Masum Miah, 2024). (Bob Foster, 2022) found green lifestyle was significant predictor of pro-environmental behaviour and indicated that employees who live sustainably are more likely to act similarly at work. Green lifestyle reflects internalization where employees translate workplace sustainability into personal responsibility (Fan Q, 2023). Weak GHRM systems may fail to convert policies into real employee engagement. Similarly, when green self-efficacy is low, this may limit employees' desire to act responsibly (Bob Foster, 2022).

Transformational and environmental leadership make significant contributions in the motivation of green behaviour among employees. (Jo, 2022) showed that environmental transformational leadership enhances the moral and cognitive ability of employees in understanding environmental matters; however, when green values are imposed from the outside, intrinsic motivation is undermined. Still, green transformational leaders inspire employees by aligning personal and organizational objectives related to environmental values. (Ali D. Abousoliman, 2025) further found that high levels of green innovation amplify the positive effect of GHRM on organizational performance. An innovation-friendly and green culture gives employees the autonomy and resources to put into place creative green ideas, thus enhancing OCBE behaviours such as eco-helping and eco-engagement.

The work setting employees' expression of organizational citizenship behaviour. (Jana Sophie Kesenheimera, 2025) found that remote work improves well-being by satisfying employees' needs for autonomy and competence. This in turn promotes helping behavior towards co-workers. This supports the premises that autonomy-driven environments might nurture eco-initiatives and eco-helping among remote employees.

Remote working increases flexibility, satisfaction, and productivity but reduces social connection, communication, and organizational culture, which are vital for eco-civic engagement (Hafsa Fatima, 2024). Similarly, (Nabriye, 2025) also found that it causes isolation, weakening the alignment of personal values with organizational value which inhibits the collaborative environmental involvement.

Perceived autonomy acts as a mediator between the advantages of working remotely and job satisfaction (Nor Lelawati Jamaludin, 2023). This indicates that employees working remotely could be more engaged in self-initiated eco-activities. Meanwhile, (Jehanzeb Khan Gurmani, 2021) suggested that eco-helping behaviours might thrive in both remote and office settings when it is nurtured by leadership support and a shared sense of meaningful work.

Rationale of the study

Organizations are increasingly adopting the sustainability goals and hence employee's enthusiasm towards green environmental activities becomes critical. COVID 19 has changed the work environment and given a boost to remote and hybrid work setting, making it important to understand how workplace location influences environmental behaviour. Existing research has talked about Green HRM practices in relation to leadership, productivity and culture. The rise of remote work means employees have different levels of autonomy, control over workspace, and exposure to organizational environmental cues. Despite these differences, very

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few empirical studies have examined whether these factors actually lead to different levels of eco-initiatives, eco-civic engagement, or eco-helping. This study helps organizations design green programs that are inclusive for both work modes.

Objectives

To examine differences between remote and office workers across the three dimensions of Green OCB: eco-initiatives, eco-civic engagement and eco- helping.

To identify whether work context influences the type of Green OCB employees engage in.

Research Methodology

Research Design:

Quantitative Cross sectional survey designed was used to compare the overall Green OCB levels of remote and office workers.

Variables:

Work setting- Remote vs office workers

- Remote Workers

Remote workers are employees who do their jobs from home or another place outside the office, using computers, phones, and the internet to communicate and complete their work.

- Office Workers

Office workers are employees who do their jobs at the company's workplace, where they meet and work face-to-face with their colleagues and supervisors.

Green organisation citizenship behaviour

Refers to voluntary, non-mandatory employee actions that support an organization's environmental goals.

Dimensions (Boiral & Paillé, 2012):

1. Eco-initiatives – It refers proactive suggestions or actions for environmental improvement.
2. Eco-civic engagement – It refers to participation in organizational environmental programs.
3. Eco-helping – It refers to helping coworkers adopt eco-friendly behaviors.

Hypothesis:

H1: Remote workers will score significantly higher on eco-initiatives than the office workers.

H2: Office workers will score significantly higher on eco-civic engagement than the remote workers.

H3: There will be no significant difference in eco-helping between the two groups.

Sample:

Employees working in IT sector aged 22 to 35 were the participants of this study. The sample size for this study was 50. Purposive, snowball and convenience sampling method was used to collect the data.

Tools for data collection:

Green Organizational Citizenship Behavior (GOCB / OCBE) scale (Boiral & Paillé, 2012, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 109(4), 431–445).

Ethical Consideration:

All the participants gave their informed consent and participation in the study was entirely voluntary. Participants' confidentiality and anonymity was maintained by ensuring that no personal identifiers were collected. Participants were debriefed about the purpose of the study. The study poses minimal risk to participants as it involves only survey-based responses regarding workplace experiences.

Scope and Limitations

The study focuses on individuals working in IT Sector aged 22 to 35 and aims to understand their Green Organizational Citizenship Behaviour. It examines three dimensions of OCB among the employees working either fully on site or fully remote. Quantitative cross sectional survey design was used to collect data and it was analysed using independent samples t- tests to compare mean scores of both the groups. Green behaviour was measured using a standardized Green OCB scale.

Sample size was one of the limitations of the study, which was relatively small and uneven across groups which may limited the statistical power and generalizability of the findings. Data was collected through self-report questionnaires, increasing the possibility of social desirability and subjective reporting. The study did not include qualitative methods which may have provided deeper insights into reasons underlying employees' sustainability practices.

Statistical Analysis

There were unequal participants in both groups, therefore variance was calculated separately for each group. Variance of office workers group for eco-initiative dimension was found to be 3.16 and for remote workers it was 4.14. Levene's test indicated that the assumption of homogeneity of variance was met, $F(1,48) = 0.46$, $p = 0.50$. Variance of office workers group for eco-civic engagement dimension was found to be 7.66 and for remote workers it was 5.06.

Levene's test indicated that the assumption of homogeneity of variance was met, $F(1,48) = 0.30$, $p = 0.58$. Variance of office workers group for eco-helping dimension was found to be 3.55 and for remote workers was 8.86. Levene's test indicated that the assumption of homogeneity of variance was met, $F(1,48) = 2.33$, $p = 0.1331$. As the assumption of homogeneity was satisfied across all dimensions, an independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the means of both groups.

The results showed that the mean eco-initiative score of remote workers (10.53) was not significantly higher compared to office workers (10.97), $t(48) = 0.79$, $p = n.s.$ The independent sample t-test did not support the hypothesis indicating that both groups engage in eco-initiatives at similar levels and autonomy while working remotely did not translate into higher sustainable behaviour. This implies that many employees, irrespective of work location, may already follow consistent environmental habits shaped by personal values, general awareness. Even office workers can adopt eco-friendly behaviours if they are internally motivated. Value belief norm states that personal environmental values and moral norms are the strongest predictors of pro-environmental behaviour more than situational factors (Stern, 2000).

Office workers had a slightly higher mean score (13.70) than the remote workers (13.06) for eco-civic engagement, but the independent samples t-test showed no statistically significant difference between two groups, $t(48) = 0.82$, $p = n.s.$ This indicates that greater exposure to organizational environmental programs did not result in higher eco-civic engagement. Even though remote workers do not physically come to the workplace, through digital communication, such as emails, virtual campaigns, etc., they can also participate in organizational green programs.

The mean scores of both the groups are nearly identical office-worker being 10.79 and remote worker being 10.88, confirming that both groups engage in eco helping at similar levels. The independent sample t test supports the hypothesis. Eco-helping is primarily a prosocial behaviour influenced by willingness to help, empathy and interpersonal motivation. Helping behaviours stem from empathic concern, which is internal and not affected by physical workplace (Batson, 1991).

Conclusion

The aim of the study was to determine whether remote workers and office workers differ in their overall levels of Green OCB. The findings showed no statistically significant differences between the two groups, suggesting that workplace location does not greatly affect

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the employees' voluntary environmental behaviours rather it is driven more by personal values, beliefs and motivation. The study further contributes to the limited research on sustainability practices in hybrid and remote work contexts. It provides evidence that green behaviours can remain consistent across different work arrangements. From a practical viewpoint, the results suggest that organizations can effectively promote sustainable behaviour among both office and remote employees.

Suggestions and recommendations

Future research can focus on wide range of professions and examine Green OCB among them to understand how occupational context affect environmental attitudes. Comparative studies involving contrasting professions might reveal sector specific patterns. Researchers can explore generational difference to understand the role of age and experience in sustainable behaviour. Furthermore, qualitative research would help to understand the nuances of why employee engage or avoid green behaviour.

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